

ENLIGHT EVs

Developing innovative and sustainable solutions to reduce EVs weight.

With 5.6 million vehicles at the end of 2021, EVs are rapidly spreading across Europe.

Reducing their weight drives down CO2 emissions, and increases range, drivability and safety.

According to experts, for electric vehicles, a 10% weight reduction generates a 10-15% increase in range.

EnLightEVs is developing innovative solutions, tested in industrial pilots, that can be rapidly applied in the automotive market to reduce EVs weight, while considering structural integrity, passengers' safety, and sustainability, through eco-design and circular practices.

To support the automotive sector in reaching these goals the cluster developed the following solutions:

Advanced lightweight materials and components for EVs

Recycled lightweight materials and end-of-life strategies

Physics and AI-based models and sensors for quality control and structural integrity assessment

Cost-effective manufacturing technologies

Eco-design strategies supported by innovative LCA tools

Innovative composite materials

Strengthened Aluminium nanocomposite for casting, extrusion and welding.

Join us on our mission to EnLight electric vehicles for a more sustainable transport sector.

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